

Flatbeds-landscape urbanism

Prof. James Corner
Roger Paez i Blanch

AAD, GSAPP, Columbia University
Summer 1999

Flatbeds-landscape urbanism

Paper one (June 3 99)

Roger Paez i Blanch
Prof. James Corner

Landscape is a genuinely contemporary cross-disciplinary field that has arisen a strong interest among very different practices, including architecture and urbanism. In doing so, merging disciplines interchange both conceptual tools and management techniques, creating novel scenarios where true innovation may occur: "landscape", rather than a discipline on its own, has become a negotiating table that frames some of the most urgent contemporary debates.

Increasingly, architects are approaching landscape as a problematic issue, rather than relegating it to a sheer "backdrop". The generalization of blurred conditions where landscape and city can no longer be understood as opposites provides an endless source of sites and materials for such practices.

A brief study of the origin of the word "landscape" allows us to rethink some general assumptions on it (i.e. greenery, parks, nature, etc).

The primitive form of the word, *landschap*, was used to refer to the XVI century pictorial genre developed by painters such as Ruysdael, where the environment for itself was the main subject of the picture.

The English translation of this German word, *landskip*, came to mean the painting of a view as opposite to the view itself. Such a notion had a very strong impact mainly in XVIII century England, where the aesthetics of the Picturesque and their voyeuristic implications¹ radically reshaped the land(scape), actually transforming a natural site to make it *look* (even more) natural, or, should one say, picture-like².

Finally, according to J.B. Jackson's analysis, the German term *landschaft*, translated into English as landscape, was coined to refer to something quite different from today's general understanding of it: rather than a view, it refers to a man-made synthetic organization of space serving a community, thereby emphasizing the performative or organizational rather than the scenic or voyeuristic; or else, stressing the "shape" of a particular milieu not in terms of appearance but rather in terms of *how* it works and *what* it does.

Landscape, then, is not at all the opposite of the city but that of the wilderness. Ultimately, a landscape refers to *ruled land*, a particular piece of land where a (man-made) law rules (this is true for countries under Roman influence. Elsewhere, one should perhaps speak about codes).

A landscape, as opposed to the formlessness of the wilderness, is a safe haven of the known world, or as Mark Cousins might put it, the *framework* where truth can happen.

A differentiation between *mobile* and *monumental* landscapes strikes as a meaningful one: the former referring to vernacular-produced landscapes as shifting terrains crudely measured, and the latter to state/power-inforced landscapes with clear-cut boundaries of sacred (or at very least sacralized) origins. According to that opposition, while monumental landscapes tend to perpetuate the status quo, and actually act as a coercive tool to do so, vernacular landscapes appear as systems that adjust to changing circumstances over time, and thus are primarily concerned with mobility and change.

Some contemporary thinkers have dealt with landscape as a subject in a number of ways that greatly affect architectural practice. Namely, Jackson, Lyotard and Koolhaas have pinpointed some very urgent issues.

Jackson's stressing of the functional or performative role of landscape as opposed to its pictorial or voyeuristic role, sets the basis for a transformative landscape-urbanism.

J-F Lyotard's analysis of the city-landscape (there is no possible segregation anymore) as an environment where one is always in a "distracted state"³, and so acts as a "lost traveller", renders impossible the distance that would allow one to differentiate the viewer from the seater (using Berger's terminology), that is, oneself (safely looking from the outside of the scene) and the environment (as the scene looked at).

Koolhaas, finally, summarizes or represents a generalized malaise with regards to mainstream (and not so mainstream) contemporary architecture, in stressing the performative and organizational pragmatics of the city.

It is a widespread sensation that architecture as an object-solving problem lacks interest outside a reduced circle of connoisseurs, and it definitely lacks political engagement and so the ability to⁴ transform the milieu where it takes place.

Hence the importance of a new urbanism that will (have to) be based upon mobility, adaptability, uncertainty, change, hybridization and infrastructure, so as to engage the global mobility as a *process* instead of trying to impose boundaries upon it⁵.

This new urbanism primarily irrigates fields: that is, it stages sites rather than determining them in final form, becoming a *strategic staging operator*.

The main concepts of Flatbeds (landscape urbanism), would then be, on the one hand, viewing landscapes as *verbs* instead of nouns (i.e. performative rather than scenic, staging fields rather than styling looks), and on the other *overviewing* (i.e. the view point/s that understand our milieux as many divergent voices, developing a mind set in which one is able to see the general view as a *flat* rather than vertical panorama, the flat *working surface*, the negotiating table⁶).

The *Flatbed* would then be the space of the *overview*.

¹ cf. John Berger, *Ways of Seeing*.

² cf. Relationship between Lorrain's pictures and XVIII century English gardens.

³ Although not at all so far from the so-called post-modern paradigm, Debord, Vaneigem, Constant and others, would not quite agree in the social implications derived from Lyotard's analysis. Cf. The principle of disorientation and the construction of situations as tools for political transformation through the transformation of one's approach to everyday life and milieux.

⁴

⁵ As Koolhaas himself says: to explore aggressively the new freedoms brought by our contemporary network society.

⁶ Not strictly managerial, but also organizational in a much more primal sense. Cf. Alison Smithson's tables (especially Water-lily Table and Collector's Table). Cf. Some of the Eames' experiments on indexing and recording, also known as "flat-ons".

-The seed of the American landscape: boundlessness

The American landscape finds its specificity in relation to two European paradigms of landscape, namely the Classical humanist and the Romantic tradition.

The question of the framing of depiction appears to be quite meaningful, the frame embodying the relative position of man (the observer) in relation to nature. The Classical tradition, on the one hand, depicts landscape as a setting for inhabitation, almost a backdrop for human figures that give landscape its true measure. The Romantic landscape, on the other hand, is understood as a huge force opposed to (or rather not reducible to) that of man¹, and man itself appears in the frame as a minuscule and lonely figure, usually facing the landscape, showing such asymmetrical relationship. The American landscape is usually depicted as plain boundless nature, with nobody on the frame. The kind of immensity conveyed is quite different from that of the European Romantic tradition, where landscape is understood in terms of resistance².

-Landscapes as a cultural construction: feedback

Landscape aims at physical, social and organizational environments, but it is not those environments themselves. Rather, landscape is the setting of those environments according to a cultural imagery, usually embodying a particular set of values. The American landscape embodies pragmatic mobility where Romanticism embodied the Sublime and Classical humanism the True (through the Beautiful and the Right). The depiction of landscape is a cultural act related to but not reducible to the actual landscape as shaped and used by a particular collectivity. Hence, a back and forth feedback is established between landscape and its representation³, whereby a particular landscape allows for a particular depiction of it, and, conversely, a particular representation of landscape (be it "real" or "imaginary") propels the implementation of such an image in the face of the Earth.

Andrew Wyeth's depictions of the Dupont's Estate being used as reference for the so-called "reconstruction" of so-called "original landscapes" is an example of such feedback⁴.

-The American landscape as a working landscape: pragmatic operativity

-Operational procedures: What is driving the shape of landscape ("shaped-land" according to Stillgoe) comes mainly from operational procedures such as those implemented after the National Land Survey of 1787 and those introduced from agriculture and the use of land, hence underlying the importance of logistics rather than aesthetics, or what landscape does rather than what it looks like.

-Derived aesthetics: The actual aesthetics of the American landscape are born from the acknowledgement of it being primarily a working landscape, i.e. we now discover experiential and aesthetic qualities arisen precisely from that very fact.

-Pragmaticality: To understand American landscape, infrastructure, technology and efficient use of the land are far more important than representational concerns. Such concerns only appear in a second stage, as derived from the actual effects of pragmatic procedures.

-Flexibility: The inherent pragmaticity of the American landscape calls for a high degree of flexibility in the uses it supports. To a certain extent, such flexibility implies a disregard of stability or rather a mistrust of the landscape as finished or completed.

-Ephemerality: Under such conditions, where temporality operates as a field of events as opposed to articulating a *grand recit*, ephemerality is the default condition.

-The Grid System: a case study

The grid system embodies all the above mentioned characteristics, setting up a very powerful *mobile landscape*.

Originally envisaged (by Th. Jefferson among others) as the ideal structure for democratic communities to develop⁵, it became essentially a highly efficient apparatus to settle (unclaimed) land. Nevertheless, the utopian idea of the grid system enabling stable communities gave way to a pragmatic framework in which mobility became its main characteristic, opening up a whole field of new freedoms to be explored⁶.

¹ Romantic landscapes tend to appear charged with potential forces: they are landscapes in motion or about to explode (cf. for example, K. D. Friederich's raging seas and J.M.W. Turner's "Yatch approaching the coast")

² Resistance to the contemporary deploying of industrialization and its implicit stating of the finite character of nature/natural resources. Some authors have to some extent understood Romanticism as the reaction of a Nature cornered by industrialization..

³ Representation being not only the outcome of a particular understanding of landscape, but an experimental platform for new approaches to landscape to further develop.

⁴ The medieval gardens (mainly the *hortus conclusus* type) as constructions emulating the mythical image of the Garden of Eden and/or the Hanging Gardens of Babylon are a historical example of representation of imaginary landscapes being actualized.

⁵ Although the somewhat aristocratic bias of Jefferson's ideas for the perfect settling is clearly revealed in his own work as an architect and landscape "theorist" as staged in Monticello.

⁶ The double-sided nature of the pioneer with regards to the actual exploration of mobility's freedoms remains nonetheless problematic.

Field space sets up a spatiality that diverges from that of Cartesian object-space. While in the latter coherence, contention and completeness of discreet objects build up a frame that prioritizes synoptic points of view usually related to some kind of perspectivism, field spaces are characterized by the emergence of objects from continuous fields, giving rise to organizational and experiential smoothness.

The main characteristics of field-space can be enumerated as follows:

- fields are forms of extended continuity and extensive coherence.
- fields are relatively neutral and empty (or vast and blank according to Jeff Kipnis' interpretation of R. M. Unger's terminology).
- fields are organizational planes involving time, as operative ecologies or systems of vectors.

SITE:

-Site as content: Any existing site having a latency of potential that the project might actualize in some manner (or at least might refer to), it is important to understand the site-work as strategic, the approach to a particular terrain itself as a creative act. In other words, to perceive the site as content.

-Site as representation: Any possible representation of a particular site carries already in itself a whole set of latencies, of potentialities to unfold¹.

SURFACE:

Working surfaces talk about relational structures among the parts, allowing for the gathering and organizing of vast amounts of materials in a single plane².

SCALE:

Field structures are essentially scale-less, in that what is revealed in a certain scale is not strictly operative or understandable in that particular scale, but might "jump" to other scales.

SYSTEM:

Fields stage sequences of emergencies: rather than constructing static and stable geometries they deploy systems or processes whose effects in time are recorded as space-time geometries of durational processes. Field procedures are basically systematical rather than compositional, they enact rather than represent.

ECOLOGY:

Ecology, as an inter-relational approach to systems, becomes a valuable conceptual (and operational) tool to deal with field practices. An ecology that would not limit itself to the natural world, but would embrace the cultural, the programmatic, and the operational worlds, would allow for a broader understanding of field dynamics.

INCOMPLETION:

The field is open, it is itself incomplete. Field practices involve endless arrays of construction rather than longing for a fulfilled finished state as commonly implied by traditional architectonic practice. Field practices tend to design (an indeterminate number of) stages that build up a process (catalytic, synergic, strategic, etc), rather than aiming to a pre-visualized result³.

Fields can be understood as surfaces, as horizons (constantly changing surfaces that can be worked along time, interrelating often contradictory materials).

Field practices can be understood as discipline with specific codes and conditions.

Fields can be understood as a background that physically disappears, a milieu of invisible agents that (can) have huge spatial, organizational, and formal consequences.

Field practices must be understood as means rather than ends, as a dynamic form of project approach that ultimately deals with an ethical must: *to increase diversification*. The staging of coherently different and diversely similar situations reveals the *emancipatory dimension* of field practices.

¹ As when one says that the properly posed question already carries in itself the whole horizon of possible responses.

² Needless to say, we understand plane in a logical and not geometrical way, as in *plane of consistency of multiplicities* as coined by Gilles Deleuze and Felix Guattari.

Besides, their idea of "flatness" (of a rhizome) really captures one of the most powerful aspects of the "field" as we try to conceptualize it: that of it being impossible to overcode, of the field not having any supplementary dimension than that it itself defines, and so the way in which any superimposed coding flattens back to the field transforming it through re-orientation. (cf Rhizome, by Deleuze and Guattari, especially "Principle of multiplicity" page 8 ss)

³ Which obviously denies the dynamic and unstable nature of the environment (geographical, political, economical, programmatic, etc) that frames the project, or at very least it suspends such dynamism.

Landscape today is widely acknowledged as performing a key role in the redefinition and reviving of urbanism. The discipline of urbanism, thoroughly depleted during the eighties, has become, according to architects and intellectuals from a wide political range¹, a new ground for meaningful and politically charged interventions. Landscape combined with urban infrastructure is providing the platform for a renewed urbanism, capable of producing urban orders that are relevant to novel social arrangements. Furthermore, urbanism² today being clearly more relevant than straightforward architecture, it is enacting a profound transformation of architecture as a discipline itself. Lately, architecture tends to borrow a lot of urbanism's insights, i.e. priority of staging, favour continuities, de-scaling strategies, temporality as an issue, meshwork structures, operational approach, catalytic intervention, overview.³

Urbanism (cf. footnote2) is experiencing a **shift** from the permanency – density “core paradigm” of traditional (European) urban thought to a nascent “diffused urbanity paradigm”, mainly concerned with temporality⁴ and decreasing density conditions. We are currently confronted with constructs that may be more precisely referred to as “urban phenomena” rather than “cities”. US's urbanity (mainly west of the Mississippi) can hardly be defined as city condition. It is much more accurate to talk about horizontal fields that allow for different degrees of density that range from what would traditionally be understood as city centre to countryside. Such field condition, besides being an organizational surface⁵, it constitutes a horizon of virtualities which we are only beginning to explore.

Four proposed landscape urbanism **working strategies**:

-“Events surfaces / Constructed grounds”:

Programming of surface as a way of working, rather than the particular design of architectural self-contained objects. Staging strategies, irrigating fields for further potentialities to unfold.

-“Vehicular abscesses / Infrastructural array”:

Rethinking of inter-modal exchange points and left-over interstitial infrastructural space through a sort of “residual urbanism” approach.

-“Verdant insertions / Aqueous moments”:

A.k.a. relevant introduction of greenery and water as urban-transformation tools as opposed to mere scenery. Construction of (future) sites through vegetation and water flooding, sites only detonated by intervention, but immediately engaging with farther reaching ecological processes⁶.

-“Shifting occupations / Differing densities”:

Working in changing occupancies both in shorter and longer spans of time. Consider such shifting scenario as a meaningful issue rather than as an anomalous situation of urbanity.

Capital mobility appears as a driving force leading to the displacement of the urban condition. Although capital mobility is by no means a new phenomenon, the intensification of such a process has had and it is having a massive influence upon the built environment. Most of current architectural practices actually retreat from those forces, forces that are (already) shaping the world, becoming increasingly irrelevant due to its nostalgia for a quasi-divine Architect figure and an urban condition that just does not exist anymore. Capital mobility sets up a situation that architecture and urbanism, as disciplines, need to come to terms with. Architecture and urbanism must engage the mobile and meshwork-like configuration of such contemporary condition in order to (continuing to) be relevant to the making of the living and working conditions.

¹ Cf. Kenneth Frampton's “Toward an urban landscape”, and Rem Koolhaas' “What ever happened to Urbanism?” as two examples of extremely diverging approaches (and aims) coinciding in such assertion -i.e. the relevancy of an emergent form of urbanism.

² We are referring to the relatively recent redefinition of the discipline of urbanism through landscape and infrastructure rather than schematic zoning-friendly Modernist urbanism as epitomized by the Athens Charter.

³ Cf. for example, FOA's account of their own work as published by ETSAA (Alacant University), 1998. FOA being a curious offspring of both Koolhaas and Eisenman renders the almost total coincidence of their systematization and the above trends even more meaningful.

⁴ That is, time as an issue, rather than its aestheticization through ephemerality, change and movement for themselves.

⁵ The negotiating table, cf. Footnote 5 in Flatbeds paper one, June 3 99.

⁶ We are not using the term ecological as a synonym of “environmental-friendly” but in its original scientific amoral sense.

Issues in Robert Slutzky's painting, according to Robert Slutzky:

- Topology
- Action
- Dance
- Depth
- Glow / Aura
- Tectonics
- Rhythm
- Edges
- Light
- Grids
- Articulation of fields
- Gravity
- Music(ality)
- Slow vision

Slutzky's painting (especially his recent work) has a strong formal resonance with (aerial) landscapes that immediately catches our architecturally informed / deformed eye. However, the connection between Slutzky's recent painting and flatness is established basically through the flat condition of the canvas. His painting does not seem to engage in operational flatness in the sense we are currently discussing in the course ¹. Slutzky's recent work, however suggestive of flat aesthetics may be ², is a perspectival one in some fundamental way. It works in a quite traditional paradigm, rather than operating in a truly flat setting, where any (new) connection / disturbance has an overall effect in reorganizing the whole field -i.e. any vector from an exterior "flattens" on the working field, not allowing for a supplementary dimension ³.

Gravity reveals itself in the lower part of the canvas in the form of drippings ⁴, giving an absolute orientation (and so constructing a privileged eye-position) to the painting. The upright and vertical position of the canvas is accepted as meaningful ⁵, rather than accepted as a perfectly arbitrary if common social practice. Depth and boundary issues, where one reads overlays, quilting / weaving and foreground-background oppositions, implying a perspectival spatiality, seem to be particularly contradictory with the operative flatness we are seeking. So it is the suggestion of three-dimensionality we find in three different ways. Firstly in the form of suggested axonometric projection in the early work (in the best de Stijl tradition). Secondly in certain rhythmic counterpoints suggesting different space-time position of the same object ⁶. And thirdly in the form of supposedly immanent properties of colour by which yellow and red are "pulling out" colours while blue belongs to the "pushing in" group (in the fashion of Kandinskij's classical understanding of painting as stated all too clearly in "Point and Line on the Plane" ⁷).

Having said that, the topological plays Slutzky stages in his painting seem to be much more relevant to the course's understanding of flatness than his recurring understanding of painting in the formal-instrumentalist tradition to which both Kandinskij and Albers belong ⁸. Slutzky's topological plays stage complex and very precise set of relationships (of colour, form, repetition, variation, edge condition, neighbouring, lightness, etc). Although such plays eventually acquire an aesthetic value, its original value lies in the framework that made them possible.

"The white field - The wheat field"

¹ Unlike Cy Twombly, Robert Rauschenberg, Mark Rothko or even the ever-cited Jackson Pollock.

² Although aesthetization is clearly not the author's main aim.

³ In our case, the supplementary dimension being the distance established respect the field.

⁴ "I like the idea that gravity pulls paint down", Robert Slutzky, July 1 1999, Columbia University.

⁵ Cf. Robert Slutzky's concept of "upper buoyancy" of his late paintings.

⁶ Cf. Robert Slutzky's explanation of four black rectangles of different sizes and positions as "Marcel Duchamp's "Nude descending a staircase"", the same object differed in time.

⁷ Although, to be fair with Kandinskij, one must point out that the continuous overstating of the above quoted text, a true product of its Zeitgeist, is completely undermined by his practice as a painter and even more so as a poet (Cf. "Sounds", Wassily Kandinskij) where Kandinskij (again) explicitly addresses the issue of colour.

⁸ Id est, painting being, ultimately, solely about the interplay and articulation of colour and shape on the plane of the canvas.

1-The charged site:

In the late fifties and mainly during the sixties and seventies, both art and architecture begin to understand the site as a problem in itself. The site is no longer seen merely as the receiver of the work, but as an issue to be addressed in the actual production of the work. The site, thus, rather than being a sheer enabler of the work or a setting understood as a given, becomes inextricably absorbed into the arts and the architectural thought and practice as a problematic issue (i.e. an issue whose consideration is relevant in itself).

This shift cannot be traced down to a single clear-cut cause. As Miwon Kwon puts it¹, the perceiving of the space of the art (and architecture should we add²) as a real place rather than as a blank state (i.e. the modern –and not strictly modernist- *tabula rasa*), imply a series of imperatives that account for it³.

The emergence of the site as a relevant issue (i.e. as a *thinkable* issue) is tantamount to the challenging of its innocence or neutrality. The constructed nature of the site uncovers, and so its political character. The site can no longer be accepted as a neutral given setting, but it will have to be addressed as charged: as an already filled scenario to transform through intervention, rather than as a tame location in which to insert a particular work. Thus, not only the nature of the work itself radically changes, but the “receiver”’s status: instead of implying a universal viewing subject detached from the scene where the “object”⁴ stands, site specificity ultimately places the “subject” in the same plane as the site (and so the work as a transformation of it), collapsing the (viewing) distance⁵.

2-Dispersion of location:

The actuality of location was a first stage in the creating of a sensibility towards site. The late-romantic idea of the *genius loci*, and its still subsisting outcomes in the form of “authenticity” and hence “truth” staged all too clearly a resistance against the ongoing mathematization of modernity. Rather than the rooted *genius loci*, a staggeringly nomadic *genius loci* comes into play in contemporary practices. Sites tend towards a dispersion of its actual location in favour of other kinds of identity structures as seen in recent paradigms such as the “generic city” or the ever-present “globalization”: from “place” to “debate”.

3-Site multiplicity:

The idea of a “site multiplicity” rather than a “site specificity” is tightly tied to the process described above. Ed Casey talks about “multiple sites in one place”, and Walter Benjamin’s acute perception produced sentences such as “the strength of sight sucking a hundred places from a single site.”⁶. Those authors point toward the understanding of site as a horizon, that is, site as virtuality⁷. That implies the existence of multiple places that actualize a site’s virtuality.

4-Ecology:

The question of ecology⁸ enters here: a site is defined as a system of dynamic relationships that allow for responses to unpredicted (drastic) change. That indefinite number of stagings of a particular site actually conform the site as such. The site becomes such virtuality, such horizon, defined through relationships rather than positions.

4-Transchronicity:

Carol Burns’s analysis of the notion of site⁹ pledges for a diachronic apprehension of time to counteract the present tendency to see site as a synchronic phenomenon¹⁰. Along with these two traditional time-frames through which site can be understood (and so, one can operate from), we propose the consideration of transchronicity¹¹.

Transchronic apprehension of time opens up the possibility of *operating within time*, along the lines of Benjamin’s “feeble messianic force”, taking advantage of our (feeble) redemptive power.

¹ Cf. “One Place After Another: Notes on Site Specificity”, Miwon Kwon, October, issue 80, Spring 1997.

² For, strangely enough, architecture’s reputed delay regarding the incorporation of either technological or intellectual achievements, does not seem to be quite so regarding that particular matter. The art’s first serious and conscious attempts to render the site problematic are usually placed around the wake of Minimalism in the late 60’s. Nevertheless, architects were very explicitly confronted with the problematic nature of the site as early as mid 50’s. The emergent Independent Group in England, although involving artists and architects alike, was very much aiming at architectural or urbanistical issues (Cf. “Patio and Pavilion” installation by the Smithsons, Eduardo Paolozzi and Nigel Henderson in “This is tomorrow” 1956 exhibition in the Whitechapel Art Gallery). The Smithson’s 1953 “CIAM Grille”, was produced to present to the Aix-en-Provence CIAM IX as a clear confrontation to mainstream Athens Charter-related understanding of (architectural) site. It stands out as a very early explicit attempt to rethink the site as meaningful. Along the same lines goes the first Team X programmatic document, namely the Doorn Manifesto, produced for Dubrovnik CIAM X by a team lead by the Smithsons and Aldo Van Eyck.

³ Namely: (1) “the (neo-avant-garde) aspiration to exceed the limitations of traditional media as well as their institutional setting”, (2) “the epistemological challenge to relocate meaning from within the art object to the contingencies of its context”, (3) “the radical restructuring of the subject from an old Cartesian model to a phenomenological one of lived bodily experience”, and (4) “the self-conscious desire to resist the forces of the capitalist market economy, which circulates art works as transportable and exchangeable commodity goods.” Cf. Miwon Kwon, op. cit.

⁴ Conceptually free-standing object. In the case of architecture, although not so obviously as in the arts, it is quite clear which buildings aspire to a certain “free-standing” objectual quality.

⁵ The “subject” at work here cannot relate to its milieu through objectification (i.e. transforming things into objects, in the heideggerian sense), and so in a sense loses its classical modern subjectivity. Hence the use of quotation marks.

⁶ The original context is that of the use of drugs to alter perception: “the opium smoker or the haschisch eater experiences the strength of sight sucking a hundred places from a single site.” Cf. “Uber Haschisch”, Walter Benjamin.

⁷ We are obviously using Deleuze’s notion of the “virtual”, or more accurately, “actualization of the virtual”.

⁸ Ecology –and not Ecologism particularly-, is a useful mind-set to think site. Ecology models a framework of operational procedures where Carbon-based organic life itself is a particular case of a much larger self-sustaining dynamical system.

Cf. Manuel de Landa, “A Thousand Years of Non-linear History”. De Landa accounts for particular organizations in fields as apparently disconnected as geology, biology and culture through the same abstract machines, i.e. lava, gene and word are accounted for from a consistent operational framework.

⁹ Cf. “On Site: Architectural Preoccupations”, Carol J. Burns.

¹⁰ Cf. Desa Philippi, “Invisible Sites”: “site” has come to mark a particular conjunction where the temporal is eroded by the spatial and where history becomes the isolated image of its residues.”

¹¹ “Transchronic” is a neologism somehow informed by both “Transgressive” and “Transversal”.

Flatbeds-landscape urbanism

Paper seven (July 21 99)

Roger Paez i Blanch
Prof. Michel Desvigne

-"Devices that trap phenomena"

Our awareness of the esthetical qualities of natural formations lies on their embodying phenomena. A "natural shape" is beautiful because it is the unmediated result of active phenomena, or in Michel Desvigne and Christine Dalnoky's own words, "a dune is beautiful because it is intimately bound up with the law of thermodynamics"¹. Thus, D+D understanding (and hence use) of landscape is a procedural one: landscape is relevant as a framework insofar it engages with the actual forces that shape it. Landscape is somewhere in the feedback between the informing agents and the perceptual outcome: a dune is wind and sand in a particular feedback relationship.

It comes as no surprise D+D's reverence for natural formations, especially those clearly involving the above mentioned feedback, acting almost as precarious cartographies of a given set of shifting intensities in a field². Thus, D+D propose the *production* of natural shapes through "devices that trap phenomena", engaging with the actual forces that shape the landscape, rather than a compositional approach that sets up a representational relationship with regards to nature. The main distinction at play here seems to be the design target and the nature of the resulting landscape. Where a conventional practice would actually *design* the (perceptual) landscape itself, D+D propose to design mechanisms of friction with the environment that will eventually produce a landscape. Landscape is thus *produced* as an outcome of clearly artificial constructions that act as mechanisms of friction with the environment. Landscape is kept alive (and hence "authentic" and "true") in not determining it as appearance but engaging with it as process (or rather network of processes)³.

-"Transposition de l'existant"

Desvigne's "substitution process" design methodology stems from two separate issues related nonetheless through the issue of authenticity: the understanding of landscape as a bearer of memory, and the resistance to overdrawing and stereotyping.

In Manuel Delluc's words, "a landscape is the bearer of a complex memory that is preserved in its every aspect"⁴. Such memory is a memory of the natural and cultural forces that are behind the current appearance of a given landscape. Understanding a landscape is a key issue to transform it: "to discern the reasons behind its particular formation, so that those same factors can then be employed as elements in the design"⁵. Memory is then the inner structure of landscape, and being true to such memory means to engage it in transforming it, not to preserve it as a dead aestheticized image of a previous state of the question. According to D+D, "The landscape designer [...] is first of all the guarantor of the *authenticity* of the landscape on which he or she acts, changing it."⁶ Authenticity, thus, being closely related to the acknowledgement of the constructed nature of landscape, and the further engaging in such construction⁷. Along the same lines Desvigne expresses the need to resist one the one hand the overdrawing of landscapes, and on the other the invasion of stereotypes. Rather than drawing landscapes, the interest is shifted towards projecting artificial built structures engaging with natural processes where landscape results as an *outcome*, and hence the intensity of the design process lies in its operational and even logistical conditions as opposed to scenic and representational ones. Overdrawing stands for (over)determining landscape. Rather than dead -if pleasant to the eye- backdrops, alive⁸ landscapes are staged as *working fields*. The stereotyping of landscape is to be resisted because stereotypes refer to once-upon-a-time alive landscapes from whose working nature they gather their legitimacy in the form of "fake authenticity".

¹ Cf. Michel Desvigne and Christine Dalnoky "Induced Transformations", IFLA Copenhagen 1999.

² "We do not want to imitate nature. We are fascinated by certain places where constant and spectacular upheavals make the drawing of maps impossible: lagoons, deltas, banks and shores, gullies." Michel Desvigne and Christine Dalnoky, op. cit..

³ "Attempts to reproduce these forms [dunes, lagoons, deltas] are inevitably failures: immobilized, *stripped of their mechanisms*, they are reduced to mere abstraction and *are dead*." Michel Desvigne and Christine Dalnoky, op. cit. Added italics.

⁴ Cf. Manuel Delluc "Michel Desvigne and Christine Dalnoky".

⁵ Cf. Manuel Delluc, op. cit..

⁶ Cf. Manuel Delluc, op. cit.. Added italics.

⁷ "the pictorial impulse denies deeper modes of existence, interrelationship, and creativity; [...] it seriously limits the design and planning arts in more critically shaping alternative cultural relationships with the earth." James Corner, "Eidetic Operations and New Landscapes" in "Recovering Landscape", Princeton Architectural Press 1999.

⁸ Alive, i.e. engaged with forces, processes and phenomena actually transforming the milieu.

"[Borges] simply dispenses with the least obvious, but most compelling, of necessities; he does away with the site, the mute ground upon which it is possible for entities to be juxtaposed. (...) What has been removed, in short, is the famous "operating table"; (...) the table upon which, since the beginning of time, language has intersected space."¹

What strikes as most powerful of the flatbed concept is its ability to reorganize itself in a horizon(tal) way, whereby the flatbed acts as horizon rather than as overarching category. Its modes of operation are closer to enabling than to encompassing.

According to its particular affiliations in a given framework, the flatbed operates in severely distinct manners, irreducible albeit somehow participating in the same dynamic and procedural understanding of our environment². An understanding whose proliferational nature obstructs the sheer possibility of the flatbed becoming a cohesive paradigm along the lines of those modernity has accustomed us to.

Thus, the "flatbed" concept per se becomes interesting through its shifts and swerves when used in different frameworks such as representation, methodology, organization, site/locus or production. The subsisting (or insisting should we say) aspects seem to play a significant role against the overrode and overriding ones, and the small differences and loose affiliations revealed through such a nomadic use of the flatbed, play a more important part in its "definition" than overarching assertions and oppositions.

Nevertheless, a series of recurring characteristics can be pointed out as relevant to the nature of flatbed (or rather, as it has been occasionally used, "flatbed-thinking"):

-*Procedure*: Process embedded in its very core, drastically re-orientating current practices based on a kind of fetishistic "result ethics". Issues such as authorship, control, and (over)determination, closely related to the understanding of process as means to an end rather than as actual state of the question, are substantially undermined under a flatbed approach.

-*Connectivity*: At any level, including a certain emancipatory dimension of flatbed practices so as to increase connectivity aiming at total interrelation and networking. Issues of speed and surveillance underlie connectivity³.

-*Collapse*: Flatbed working conceptually in a collapsed condition not allowing for a supplementary dimension⁴. Most importantly, a depth issue is raised here. The *collapsed depth* pertains to the flatbed condition rather than mere flatness, be it staged in a drawing or in a negotiating table.

-*Proliferation*: Any stage defined by a provisional stability relating to its current boundary conditions and its affiliative chart. A deterministic approach thus obstructed, ultimately deconstructs the very idea of design as we know it, maintaining nonetheless the ground for critical thought and action under the form of will⁵. Moreover, the instrumental use of the flatbed is provisional and precarious, as its proliferational character obstructs its harnessing under the form of instrumentalization.

Flatbed frameworks (a provisional list):

- (0) *Representation*: flatbed as understanding of imaging, using representation as an actually instigative force "actively participating in emergent realities"⁶.
- (1) *Methodology*: flatbed as understanding of design approach in and of itself.
- (2) *Organization*: flatbed as understanding of mode of labour, whereby traditional disciplines such as architecture and urbanism are re-arranged in new forms of practice.
- (3) *Site/Locus*: flatbed as understanding of site in the sense of Foucault's *tabula*⁷, where site, rather than a setting, becomes an enabling field, a horizon of consistency, a linking device.⁸
- (4) *Production*: flatbed as understanding of the products or provisional results of practice, and hence their own modes of operation within a given framework, such as their ability to produce new affiliations.

¹ Cf. Michel Foucault, *The Order of Things*, Preface, page xvii

² We are using the word "environment" in its most ample sense, one including language as a "force" comparable to geological drifts and climatic conditions in its overall shaping.

³ Paradoxically enough, faced with an ongoing globalization, connectivity seems to allow for a degree of non-marginal resistance. Contemporary terrorism operates through connection rather than isolation. The question addressed here is primarily that of Toni Negri's "to run away but pointing a gun", or the impossibility (or unrelevancy for that matter) of true marginality. The escalating proliferation of connectivity thus appears with a certain scent of liberatory character, albeit one completely different than that played out by, say, a marxist-based revolution.

⁴ We are obviously drawing heavily on Gilles Deleuze and Felix Guattari's conceptualization of the rhizome. Cf "Rhizome: an Introduction", *A Thousand Plateaux*.

⁵ The issue of "will" and its relationship with efficacy will be further researched in the upcoming paper, Cf. "Flatbeds-Paper 9: Horizontal Societies and Network Practices".

⁶ Cf. James Corner, "Eidetic Operations and New Landscapes" in "Recovering Landscape", page 153 and 159.

⁷ Cf. Michel Foucault, "Preface", in "The Order of Things", pages xvi-xx especially.

⁸ Along the same lines one can understand Alex Walls's take on the "urban surface", where such field becomes the common locus, the agent of consistency of the urban condition in the very same way as Eusthene's saliva is the common locus of "all these worms and snakes":

"The excessive and inclusive ground-plane of the city, (...) the "field" (...) that organizes and supports a broad range of fixed and changing activities in the city." Alex Wall "Programming the Urban Surface", in "Recovering Landscape", page 233.

"But all these worms and snakes, all these creatures redolent of decay and slime are slithering, like the syllables which designate them, in Eusthene's saliva: that is where they all have their *commom locus*, like the umbrella and the sewing-machine on the operating table;" Cf. Michel Foucault, op cit., page xvi.

"Chinese thinkers believed that they could detect in warfare's unfolding a purely internal necessity that could be logically foreseen and, accordingly, perfectly managed. (...) Chinese strategic thought stands as a perfect example of how one can manage reality, and provides us with a general theory of efficacy."¹

The idea of efficacy stemming from disposition² as conveyed by Julien reformulates the problem of action in the contemporary condition, proposing ancient Chinese strategic thought as a paradigm of efficacious acting by managing reality from its propensities, rather than imposing realities through western *enraonnement*³. But the question of efficacy, nevertheless, stands as quite problematic in the present condition of actual implementation of the modern project. In such a framework, efficacy is tinted not only with morality, but most importantly with ontological pretensions. Efficacy, in itself, legitimates moral adequacy, and moreover it misleadingly takes on an explanatory role of the way the world actually works⁴.

What is being criticized here is efficacy as an end in itself, and the ideal of correction it stages. The critique of correction, as articulated by Heidegger⁵, stresses the fact that correction necessarily stays within the framework in which its possibility has appeared. To respond correctly –that is, *strictly* correctly- to a given question, limits the responses to the horizon construed by the question itself. The question sets up a particular field upon which certain "thinkabilities" can virtually operate. To answer (correctly) to the question means to abide to the world it opens up, or the virtualities it allows. When correctly operating, ultimately any response is already included in the question itself as a framework.

On moral grounds, Steinberg has identified efficiency as self-justifying, exonerating any activity whatsoever: "those activities which, like bloomed and art, sometimes seem dubious on moral grounds –they more than any need the higher ideal of efficiency to shelter under."⁶. Efficacy, in and of itself, legitimates any activity, allowing for appalling actions to be rendered aseptic through the beauty of its correct implementation⁷, and perhaps more importantly, allowing for totally alienated (or un-intense for that matter) life(style)s to appear as somewhat heroic through the "ideal of a good man getting his job done without a fuss."⁸.

The understanding of work as evil (e.g. Wilde), and the ulterior radical critique of work as staged by the Situationist International⁹, calls into question its benign aspect, pinpointing work's spellbinding quality: its tendency to justify itself through its mere existence as regulated by correction and efficacy. From the late fifties on, we have seen an ongoing undermining of the very foundations upon which efficacy as an end stands. Idleness, deviation, and obstruction became keywords¹⁰. Within architectural-related disciplines, efficacy has been criticized along similar lines from very different points of view: from Alvaro Siza's claim for a slowed down design process¹¹ to Bernard Tschumi's incorporation of murder into architectural domain¹². Tschumi's statement draws very explicitly on Thomas Bernhard, whose whole production can be seen very revealingly under the light of this paper's subject matter. Bernhard's works stage an escalation of correction, revealing the hallucinatory character of exactness, precision, and efficacy when disjointed from an instrumental usage and enthroned as absolute values:

"I shall construct a building that will so match with my sister that it will kill her. The building will not be completed until the death of my sister. My sister's death will mark the completion of the building. My sister is dearer to me than my own life."¹³

Efficacy becomes a powerful tool¹⁴ when deprived of its own overriding inertia and used to stage a contention or a will¹⁵.

The preserving of will, and its (critical) relevance within the larger framework of contemporary societies, stand out as one of the most urgent issues to be addressed in current architectural practices.

When instrumentally actualizing will, efficacy loses its totalitarian shades and becomes an *enabling process*, the art of stating a will and actually "getting things done".

¹ Cf. Francois Julien, "The Propensity of Things", page 25.

² Disposition being the relationship between shape and situation through gradient. Cf. Francois Julien, op. Cit. Page 29.

³ Referring to (western post-cartesian) reason's effacing character: reason as the plough that radically re-shapes the field, engraving an overall pattern in the whole surface. Concepts such as *tabula rasa* are only thinkable within such paradigm.

⁴ See, for example, the common ontological misapplication of (modern western) science's modeling methodology.

⁵ Cf., among other works, "The Question concerning Technology", Martin Heidegger, in "Basic Writings", Routledge.

⁶ Cf. Leo Steinberg, "Other Criteria", page 60.

⁷ "It was definitely a good night's work. I don't know how many gooks we got really but we got plenty. We counted 140 on the ground this morning."

⁸ "They work in three-man teams. When they drop an enemy, each man of the team is credited with a kill." As quoted by Leo Steinberg, op. Cit. Page 60.

⁹ Refer as well to recent "clean wars" as inaugurated by the Gulf War.

¹⁰ E.g. the "family-supporting clerk who, after thirty years of unappealing work and bleak family life in an oh-so-green lower-middle class suburb, (...) complains while presumptuously theorizing to her absent-minded wife about the train-staff strike that compelled him to be half an hour late for the first time in over two years of overwhelming punctuality." Guillem Malabranca, "Atlas"

¹¹ E.g. the "right to laziness" as a collapsing of the segregation between work and leisure time, as these supposedly opposed times are revealed as operating within the frame of the spectacle, the form of deferred death imposed by capitalism. Cf. "La Societe de l'Spectacle" Guy E. Debord, "Rapport..." Guy E. Debord, and "La Creacion Abierta: Antologia de textos situacionistas".

¹² Note the already moralizing character of language, whereby these words refer *negatively* to "work, correctness, efficacy" even if they actually perform assertively.

¹³ Alvaro Siza, "Slowness", Lecture at ETSAB, Barcelona, 1992. Refer too to "A Praise to Incompetence", by Xavier Rubert de Ventos.

¹⁴ "To really appreciate architecture, you may even need to commit a murder", Advertisements for Architecture, Bernard Tschumi 1978.

¹⁵ Thomas Bernhard, excerpts from "Korrektur" (Correction).

¹⁶ "Like a pair of good scissors", to quote Peter Smithson. Cf. Peter Smithson, "On Coderch's statement "It is not geniuses what is needed nowadays""", 1996.

¹⁷ "Potentially at least, each arrangement [of Fuller's Dymaxion Airocean World Map] possesses great efficacy with regard to certain socio-political, strategic and imaginative possibilities." James Corner, "The Agency of Mapping: Speculation, Critique and Invention", page 218, in "Mappings", Denis Cosgrove, ed..